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Highly advanced modular integration of insulation, energising and storage systems for
non-residential buildings

D9.3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

WP9 Dissemination, communication and exploitation

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant agreement	EE	Energy Efficiency
M	Month	EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package	ESCO	Energy Service Company
D	Deliverable	TBC	To Be Complete
EEB	Energy Efficient Buildings		

1. Summary

This document deliverable D9.3 “Communication and Dissemination Plan” presents the POWERSKIN+ project communication and dissemination strategy and is designed as an internal practical guide for project partners for engaging with communication and dissemination. The present document constitutes the first issue of Communication and Dissemination Plan in the framework of the POWERSKIN+ project, dedicated to Task 9.1 “Communication and dissemination” under the work package WP9 “Dissemination, communication and exploitation”. The update of this Plan will be done on a yearly basis, shared with partners and finally at the end of the project will result in the D9.8 “Communication and Dissemination report and Awareness campaign”.

2. Introduction

The objective of the Communication and Dissemination Plan is to identify and organize the activities planned in order to promote the commercial exploitation of the project’s results and the widest dissemination of knowledge from the POWERSKIN+ project. The Plan is expanded in two directions: towards the marketing activities to enhance the commercial potential of the technology and towards the notification of project results in the scientific, EC and general R&D sector. This document summarizes the consortium’s strategy and concrete actions to disseminate and communicate the results generated by the POWERSKIN+ project. Moreover, information related to the Communication and Dissemination Plan aiming to raise the public awareness on the project results and to demonstrate to the potential end-users the advantages of the new products/technologies is presented. The Plan sets out which dissemination activities had already been achieved and provides an outline of what is planned until the end of the Project. This report is dependent also on the deliverable D9.4 „Data Management Plan” which identifies the results that should be subject of dissemination and exploitation and analyses the main data uses, users and explore the restrictions related to IPR according to the Consortium Agreement.

An overview of dissemination opportunities was identified through traditional channels such as event attendance and organization (e.g. conferences, seminars, workshops, fairs, etc.), project publications (e.g. brochures, posters, press releases as well as conference papers, articles in professional journals, etc.) and project presentations, also complemented by online activities based around the project website, newsletter, and through the main social media profiles. The dissemination activities were designed to target the key audiences and stakeholders and to maximize awareness of the POWERSKIN+ project and its results.

FIGURE 1: POWERSKIN+ DISSEMINATION PURPOSE

3. Obligation to disseminate the project results

As stated in POWERSKIN+ Grant Agreement article 29, unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must - as soon as possible - disseminate its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications. A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of - unless agreed otherwise - at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within - unless agreed otherwise - 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests. If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may - under certain conditions - need to formally notify the Commission before dissemination takes place. Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- a) as soon as possible or, at the latest, on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

- b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
- i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

4. Communication and dissemination strategy

One of the main goals of WP9 is to reach the widest dissemination of the results generated by the POWERSKIN+ project and raise public awareness on the energy efficiency of non-residential buildings - insulation technologies, nanomaterials, advanced materials and processes, energy harvesting and storage in retrofitting solutions. In this framework, a strong communication strategy was set up in order to make the most of reaching the target impact. The whole POWERSKIN+ consortium is committed to perform dissemination activities and proactively look for dissemination opportunities. Communication activities aim at creating a common project visual identity and public image, to raise basic interest in the proposed technology and processes, to provide up-to-date information about the project, translate the scientific/technical results into messages that can be read by a wide public.

Dissemination actions will be carried out in three main phases:

1) Establishing interactions with relevant stakeholders and related projects

Specific dissemination and communication activities will be developed in order to strengthen the cooperation with the main stakeholder communities involved in the complex supply chain of the POWERSKIN+ project, both at EU and member state level. These communities consist of a wide variety of players, such as the EC, policymakers, professional representatives, public authorities, sectorial and industry associations,

educational institutions and society in general, thus dissemination activities might be tailored in the function of the considered stakeholder. Moreover, a link with other relevant EU co-funded projects will be established in order to improve the cooperation among EEB, Smart Cities and EE projects by exchanging information, sharing methodologies and avoiding overlapping between the projects. Attracting industrial stakeholders is invaluable in this respect, because the future replication and market penetration of the POWERSKIN+ technology will depend on them. Conferences, workshops, seminars and clustering events will be organized to target a broad stakeholders' audience. POWERSKIN+ will gain feedback on on-going/foreseen development activities, inputs related to research findings, existing tools, best practices and market, and input on future regulations and policies. This huge category of stakeholders includes building owners, facility managers, European and international associations, architects' associations, construction companies, etc. as well as national and regional Energy Agencies, European Construction Technology Platform and Energy Efficient Buildings European Initiative, technology providers and other intermediaries, such as the National Contact Points and the Energy Enterprise Network. Moreover, the POWERSKIN+ project will also foresee the engagement of end-users to help the consortium in defining the market needs and giving feedback on the developed tools (private clients, key users, ESCO companies). Last but not least, dissemination and communication activities will also target the engagement of facilitators, with the final aim of offering to clients the advantage of the developed systems, policymakers and public procurers (promoters, local authorities and National/Regional public).

2) Raising social acceptance and unlocking of current barriers

Link with institutions will be established through lobbying activities with governmental and public authorities at the various levels (European, national, regional/local). Dialogue with relevant EU and national institutions will be established by tailored dissemination activities in order to create substantial technical expertise to unlock the potential current legislative barriers that might hinder the future utilization of the demonstrated technology. The social context by the introduction of tailored dissemination activities such as questionnaires aiming to identify the end user's point of view. The social acceptance will also be tackled by the creation of the project videos, publications in scientific and technical journals and organization of conferences, workshops, seminars and other events.

3) Interacting with the scientific community and professionals

Especial attention will be paid to all players involved in the transfer of the acquired knowledge and the future market deployment. For this purpose, training activities will be organized in order to ensure the correct training of those professional figures involved in the demonstration of the developed technology, from the design and production to the application and installation. Dedicated courses and webinars, as well as seminars directly held at the demo sites, will be organized. Moreover, communication activities will target the scientific community through the organization of workshops and through the publication of the main achievements of the project in scientific and technical journals with high impact.

4.1 Target audience and stakeholders

The main focus for all dissemination activities is on the Energy efficiency in buildings - nanotechnologies, advanced materials and processes, insulation and the building sector in general. Possible target groups will be all players involved in the construction industry and renovation projects:

- Public authorities (local, municipal authorities granting building permits)
- Investors (financial institutions, bankers, project developers)
- Service providers (thermo-technical companies, engineers, construction companies, ESCOs)
- Industry/Manufacturers (raw materials producers, heat battery manufacturers/providers, installers, reactor components and other equipment)
- Civil society/End-users (building managers, public buildings owners, architects and architects' associations, sector and industry associations, potential early users)
- Standardization/certification bodies (technical chambers, National standard organizations)
- Experts (ECTP experts and EEB experts, other EU funded research project partners, researchers in the field)

The role of the target groups will be to give feedback on on-going and foreseen development activities, bring useful inputs related to research findings, existing tools, best practices and market evolution, to help to define the market needs. A stakeholder can be anyone who has an interest in the project or is affected by its outcomes. Different groups of stakeholders for POWERSKIN+ project were identified and assessed in terms of their interest in the project and the importance for its success and further dissemination. Communication efforts will be spread among the whole sector: building managers (reduced energy bills, reduced maintenance cost), ESCOs/energy providers (new channels for additional customer-facing services), municipalities, policymakers (reduced energy demand), National and Regional Energy Agencies, European Construction Technology Platform, etc..

4.2 Key messages

Key messages that the POWERSKIN+ project wants to give to the targeted audience and stakeholders were defined, following the communication principles as shown on the graphic below. Key messages were agreed between partners and will be demonstrated through the project website, brochure, flyer, poster, newsletter, video, etc.

FIGURE 2: POWERSKIN+ KEY MESSAGES

4.3 Tools

Dissemination activities will be targeted both nationally and internationally. The tools that will be used for dissemination are the following:

- Publications (scientific, technical and economical journals, popular magazines, newspapers)
- Conferences, congresses, workshops, seminars, forums participation
- Fairs, exhibitions participation
- Public workshops, webinars organization
- Press releases
- Digital (project website, social media profiles, thematic portals, online ads will also be considered)
- Links to other projects, clustering activities
- Common visual identity, logo, brochure, poster, project presentation
- Video production (project promo videos, videos from the events, training videos)
- E-newsletters, infographics
- Gadgets for promotion
- Training sessions, webinars, etc.

4.4 Commitment of project partners

POWERSKIN+ partners involved in dissemination will proactively participate in communication and dissemination activities related to the Project by exploiting their communication channels to reach the widest audience performed in a structured way, and all these activities will be tracked in this report and its updates. Each dissemination activity will be carried out by the partner who is the most expert in the specific area. For the tracking of the actions executed by POWERSKIN+ partners, a set of tools for the collection of inputs in regard to performed and planned activities has been developed:

- List of scientific publications - table a) of Figure 3
- List of dissemination events and activities - table b) of Figure 3
- Detailed description of events already performed - table c) of Figure 3.

Each partner is required every six months to provide updated information about dissemination events and activities performed and planned by his organization. Partners need to provide to the dissemination leader (FENIX) proofs about events participation (photos, agendas, presentations, videos, etc.) and also detailed information about the events (date, place, target audience, size of the audience, type of dissemination such as ppt, brochure, poster, booth, etc.). Project partners are also requested to provide updates about the project progress and achievements in order for the POWERSKIN+ website and promo material to be kept up to date.

Table 1: List of publications

Publication title	Link	Publication type	DOI	ISSN or eSSN	Authors	Periodical name/ Publisher	Number, Date	Place	Relevant pages	Public & private participation	Peer/revie w	Open access; cost of	Partner/s	Status
Title of the article	Website link if applicable	(paper in conference, article in journal, books/monographs, chapters in books, thesis, etc.)	Digital Object Identifier	Number	Full names of the authors	Or equivalent	of journal of publication	of article		YES/NO	YES/NO	YES (green, gold)/NO	As in GA	(Performed/Planned)

a)

Table 2a: List of dissemination events and activities

Type of event/activity	Link	Event/activity title	Objective	Date	Place	Partner contribution	Countries addressed	Target audience and size	Partner/s	Status
Conference, fair, workshop, social media, website, thematic portal, press release, newsletter, etc.	Website link if applicable	Official title of the event/activity description	Reason why participated/organized event/performed activity	Date of the event/activity performed	Place of the event/activity	(speech, ppt, poster, brochure, stand, etc.)	(national/international)	Scientific community, industry, ESCOs, etc.	As in GA	(Performed/Planned)

b)

Table 2b: Proof of events already performed	
Event title	
Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)	

c)

FIGURE 3: TEMPLATES FOR DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES, EVENTS AND PUBLICATIONS TRACKING

4.5 Evaluation

Dissemination activities are targeted and can be more or less successful. To find out if the dissemination strategy was well chosen and well implemented, it is important to build an evaluation component into all major dissemination activities to monitor the quality and to see if they have achieved their aims. Some key performance indicators have been defined as the table below shows.

TABLE 1: POWERSKIN+ SUCCESS KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Dissemination activity	Description	KPI (end of the project)
Project website	Created in M3 it serves as a place for storing, sharing and downloading public documents related to the project as well as provides an opportunity for the general public to get updated information about the project. It will be kept alive and maintained for at least 2 years after the project ends.	> 20 000 views > 2 000 users
Social media campaign	Created in M1 and updated on a weekly basis (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram).	In total: > 500 followers > 150 000 impressions
Project brochure, roll-up and presentation	Designed in M5, including general public information about the project. Three updates of the promo materials planned within the project. The brochures will be available for the attendees of the dissemination events and the roll-up will serve as the visual representation of the project	> 5000 printed copies > 500 downloads from the project website

e-Newsletter	Distributed among the relevant actors every six months (starting at M8) including the project updates, findings, and outcomes of the researches performed under the project as well as other interesting information about the project.	> 500 subscribers and downloads from the project website
Videos	Two promo videos are planned. In M2, a graphical video illustrating the project objectives, concept, demos and partners created. At M36, the video including interviews with key partners and footage from the demo sites will be produced.	In total: > 600 views on YouTube channel
Publications	Articles in dedicated journals and magazines in the field of energy efficient buildings, construction sector. Press releases in the thematic portals.	> 5 scientific papers > 5 articles in magazines > 10 press releases
Training activities	Webinars and dedicated courses at the demo sites aimed at explaining the manufacturing, design, installation of the project technology. Creation of training video, guidelines as a booklet.	> 3 Education and/or training courses
Cluster activities	Clustering activities with other European related projects and related European and National Technology Platforms, associations such as ECTP, ECCREDI, and FIEC).	> 3 Participation and organization of events
Organization of conferences or workshops	One public workshop will be organized towards the end of the project involving representative cities, industries, and EU officials.	> 1 public workshop organization with > 70 participants
Participation at exhibitions, fairs, seminars, workshops, or conferences	Representation and exhibition of the project at various types of events. The purpose is to spread awareness about the project as well as to answer questions about particular research results.	> 30 various events participation

5. Project identity and public image

Objectives of the project identity are:

- To develop a design structure that would accommodate standard project identity elements, a variable visual identity in various uses, and be able to convey thematic information when needed
- To allow immediate recognition of the POWERSKIN+ project, thanks to standardized communication templates meant for external audiences.

- To develop specific guidelines and structures related to the project, such as a definite set of colours and/or typography. These guidelines should be applied to templates that are easy to adapt, to understand and to use by the project partners.

Visual and graphic point of view allows a more straightforward identification for the public as well as easier visibility to obtain a branding for the POWERSKIN+ project during the dissemination activities as shown in the following section.

5.1 Project logo and logo manual

The logo has been created by FENIX in vector resolution at the beginning of the project, in order to define a distinguishable project identity. The original logo was designed by IPN during the proposal stage. The logo was intended to be simple and recognizable. While designing the logo, it was important for FENIX that it reflects the actual branding trends, so that the design is up to date during the whole project lifecycle. It was kept in mind, that the target audience must identify the logo at first glance, therefore the logo should be easy to remember, and it must clearly reflect the aim of the project.

The simplified image of the “building” symbolized by three thick lines is joined by the name of the project situated inside. The chosen typeface is strong and thick to go along with the motive of three thick lines, that represent a building envelope.

For the purpose of the project, two basic versions of the POWERSKIN+ logo were created. The **main logo** is oriented horizontally, and the name of the project is followed by the main motto of the project “walls energizing buildings.” Simplified **square version** will be used on social media and all the graphics with the logo width under 26mm.

FIGURE 4: POWERSKIN+ MAIN LOGO

FIGURE 5: POWERSKIN+ SQUARE LOGO

The logo uses three colours: orange, black, light grey regular white. The POWERSKIN+ logo font is Rubik bold.

FIGURE 6: PALETTE OF COLOURS USED

It is essential to follow and respect the project visual identity to maximize the impact on the audience. For this reason, a logo manual has been created, outlining the visual identity guidelines (master brand logo, colour palette, logo usage, logo clear zone, relation to other logos, typography, file formats, applications and errors to avoid).

The logo and logo manual can be downloaded from the project website:

<https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials/logos>

FIGURE 7: POWERSKIN+ LOGO MANUAL

As stated in the POWERSKIN+ Grant Agreement and article 27.3 Information on EU funding applications for protection of results (including patent applications) filed by or on behalf of a beneficiary must - unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible - include the following:

“The project leading to this application has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869898”.

FIGURE 8: EU LOGO

5.2 Project website

The POWERSKIN+ website is considered in WP9 as one of the key elements for communication. The website is hosted by FENIX though domain powerskinplus.eu. The design was developed by FENIX with the collaboration of the consortium. The website was designed in month M3 considering display on different devices such as desktop, mobile or tablet. The information included on the project website is likely to be valuable even after the project has finished. Therefore, the consortium aims at ensuring that the website will continue to exist after the project funding has finished (minimum 2 years).

FIGURE 9: POWERSKIN+ WEBSITE

The website has been designed by FENIX and the main aim was to quickly address the key questions that external visitors to the website are expected to have:

- What is the project about?
- Who is participating in the project?
- What additional details are available?
- Who to contact for more information?

The website itself contains the following information:

- general information about the project and demo sites,
- partners' details,
- list of news and events,
- all public material that is generated by the project,
- links to social network profiles, twitter feed online,
- newsletter subscription,
- contact information,
- videos and gallery.

Website cookies policy and google analytics tracking were also implemented (number of visitors, users, sessions, countries, languages, downloads, etc.). Short term improvements to the website are mainly: update of the website content based on project progress annually (and on-demand, when it is necessary), project video implementation. More information about the project website is in the deliverable D9.1 “Project website”.

5.3 Project dissemination material

FENIX designed promo material in English from month M2 to M5 to support partners in dissemination events and raise awareness about the project, specifically a leaflet, brochure, roll-up poster and a PowerPoint presentation. This promo material will be updated a minimum of three times per project duration to provide readers with the latest information and news about POWERSKIN+. More details about POWERSKIN+ dissemination material can be found in deliverable D9.2 “Promo material”.

The promo material can be downloaded from the project website:

<https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials>

FIGURE 12: POWERSKIN+ ROLL-UP POSTER

FIGURE 13: POWERSKIN+ PRESENTATION

6. Videos

One of the key methods for the effective product dissemination is the creation and publication of videos. Video is the most popular format in online marketing as of 2020. FENIX with in-house video production will lead the creation of videos for POWERSKIN+ project. Two promo videos, and few short videos from the demo sites are planned. A [graphical video](#) was created in month M2 to support dissemination activities from the

beginning of the project. The promo video is planned to be designed towards the end of the project when the technology is fully developed and tested at demo sites. It will include interviews, photos, filming, graphics, music and voice over. The main aim of the videos will be introducing the POWERSKIN+ project to a wide public audience (project introduction, main objectives, innovation, design, demo versions, advantages, use, and contact info). The video presentation is meant to follow the successive introduction to the strategies regarding the “online campaigns”: social media, workshops, web advertising in general. The videos will be then implemented into the POWERSKIN+ project website, uploaded on the [YouTube channel](#) and shared on social profiles, thematic portals, among partners, presented during events, etc. The slideshow from the graphical video created by FENIX at month M2 is below.

The project is also planning cooperation with **Euronews** once the technology is developed and results from the demo sites are obtained.

FIGURE 14: POWERSKIN+ INTRODUCTION VIDEO

7. E-Newsletter and press release

An E-newsletter will be designed by FENIX with technical contribution of project partners, the first release is planned at M8 and then every 6 months. Each partner will share the newsletter among their contacts. The newsletter will be directly sent to the POWERSKIN+ subscribers who subscribed through the project website and also published on social network profiles, project website, thematic portals, etc. Newsletter subscription will follow the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regarding the protection of personal data.

8. Social media campaign

Willing to raise public awareness about the POWERSKIN+ project, different social network profiles were evaluated as the most suitable and created at month M1 on LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, YouTube and Instagram. Associated links were added into the project website, and the profiles are being updated with posts every week by FENIX, based on the partners' contribution (updates about the project progress, photos from dissemination activities – fairs, conferences, workshops, etc.) or with info related to the project topic. At month M6 the statistics are: 160 followers in total and 16 984 impressions. As the project progresses, paid ad campaigns will be considered to boost the most important posts to reach the maximum amount of target audiences. Public workshop invitation, crucial project progress reports and other milestones will be considered for paid ads campaigns.

FIGURE 15: POWERSKIN+ SOCIAL MEDIA PROFILES

9. Publications

As stated in GA's Article 29.2, each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

- a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

- b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

- c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable;
- a persistent identifier.

Partners are going to publish articles about the POWERSKIN+ project in popularized and technical magazines. Other publications are planned in the thematic portals (e.g. BuildUp, EUAgenda, Construction21), Projects magazine, Horizon 2020 Projects, Horizon - The EU Research and European Energy Innovation magazine. Project partners will publish the results also in the scientific literature and dedicated journals. POWERSKIN+ publications will be made accessible through either the Green Open Access or Gold Access model in accordance with H2020 guidelines on Open Access.

9.1 Green open access

The green open access is also called self-archiving and it means that the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived by the researcher in an online repository before, after or alongside its publication. Access to this article is often delayed (embargo period). Publishers recoup their investment by selling subscriptions and charging pay-per-download/ view fees during this period during an exclusivity period. This model is promoted alongside the “Gold” route by the open access community of researchers and librarians and is often preferred.

9.2 Gold open access

This type of open access is sometimes called open access publishing, or author pays publishing, and means that a publication is immediately provided in open access mode by the scientific publisher. Associate costs are shifted from readers to the university or research institute to which the researcher is affiliated, or to the funding agency supporting the research. This model is usually the one promoted by the community of well-established scientific publishers in the business.

9.3 List of POWERSKIN+ publications

POWERSKIN+ partners have identified prospective journals and magazines in which they are going to publish the project results. At this stage, the list is quite short, but every six months it will be updated and extended with new publications planned and performed.

Those publications in focus:

- **REHVA Journal** (technical, practical journal for the HVAC industry professionals, read by designers, consultants, manufacturers, investors, mechanical contractors, sales and representative companies, architects, energy sector's professionals, governmental institutions authorities, etc.; bi-monthly technical publication presenting the latest developments in the European HVAC sector, with a specific focus on the energy efficiency and indoor environment of buildings and use of renewable energy sources; distributed in over 50 countries through the Member Associations and other institutions; [publisher TEKNİK SEKTÖR YAYINCILIĞI A.Ş.; readership 15,2 mill., ISSN 1307-3729; Green open access](#))
Link: <https://www.rehva.eu/rehva-journal>
- **Journal of Energy Storage** (quarterly B2B publication that covers global news, trends and developments in energy storage and smart grid markets, read by the renewables energy industry, energy utilities and grid owners, distributed network operators, high performance and advanced battery manufacturers, thermal and other storage technologies and systems, suppliers of energy storage management and control systems, policymakers and shapers, universities and research institutes, associations and alliances representing energy storage, renewables & conventional energy sectors; [publisher Elsevier BV; ISSN 2352-152X; Green open access](#))
Link: <http://www.energystoragejournal.com>
- **European Energy Innovation magazine** (communication platform designed with one purpose in mind: to put energy and transport stakeholders in touch with each other, used by workers who collaborate with EU institutions, in industry or academia, well-written informative communication keep them up-to-date with the latest thinking on energy, climate change and transport in Europe; dissemination messages can be featured on a page or double-page spread, enabling projects to reach a unique audience of 20,000 readers in energy and transport industries, Members of the European Parliament and senior EU Commission officials; [Publisher: Prologue Media Ltd., UK; ISSN: 2219-9446, ISBN: 978-92-64-28230-8; gold open access 1500EUR per page](#))
Link: <http://www.europeanenergyinnovation.eu/>
- **Journal of Facade Design and Engineering** (presents new research results and new proven practice in the field of facade design and engineering, the goal is to improve building technologies, as well as process management and architectural design, it is a valuable resource for professionals and academics involved in the design and engineering of building envelopes, including the following disciplines: architecture, façade Engineering, climate design, building services integration, building physics, façade design and construction management, novel material applications, the journal will be directed at the scientific community, but it will also feature papers that focus on the dissemination of science into practice and industrial innovations; [Publisher: TU Delft Open, Netherlands; ISSN 2213-302X print, 2213-3038 online, green open access](#))
Link: <https://journals.open.tudelft.nl/index.php/jfde/>

- **Intelligent Glass Solutions magazine** (one of the leading magazines in the glass industry bringing you the latest news, technologies and developments in the architectural glass and facade design and construction field. Readers enjoy content from authentic leaders of the industry, featuring amazing architecture predominantly focused on glass, with exclusive content that is rarely obtainable elsewhere; Publisher: Intelligent Publications Limited (IPL), UK; ISSN 1742-2396, gold open access)
Link: <https://igsmag.com/>
- **Open Journal of Energy Efficiency** (the goal is to provide a platform for scientists and academicians all over the world to promote, share, and discuss various new issues and developments in all areas of energy efficiency, the areas covered include: consumer behaviour and the dynamics of consumption; energy efficiency; energy efficiency in the building issues; energy efficiency policies; energy management systems and energy services; energy planning and risk assessment, power usage effectiveness; Online ISSN: 2169-2645, Print ISSN: 2169-2637; green open access)
Link: <https://www.scirp.org/journal/OJEE/>
- **Energy and buildings journal** (international journal publishing articles with explicit links to energy use in buildings, the aim is to present new research results, and new proven practise aimed at reducing the energy needs of a building and improving indoor environment quality, Energy and Buildings considers and publishes articles considerably advancing Building Science, topics covered include: Energy demands and consumption in existing and future buildings, indoor environment quality, natural, mechanical and mixed ventilation, air distribution in buildings, application of solar and other renewable energy sources in buildings, energy balances in building complexes, energy efficiency improvement measures of HVAC&R and other technical systems in buildings, and semi-open built spaces, heat recovery systems in buildings, buildings and district heating and cooling, energy efficient buildings, energy sustainability, resilience and climate adaptability of buildings, etc.; Publisher: Elsevier, Switzerland; ISSN 0378-7788; green open access)
Link: <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/energy-and-buildings>
- **The Project Repository Journal** (the European Dissemination Media Agency's (EDMA) flagship open access publication dedicated to showcasing funded science and research throughout Europe, distributed quarterly and on a free of charge basis to a global audience of over 200,000 people, with features discussing current and future funding calls, science policy, European and World-Wide Initiatives and research news it will bring together prolific members of academia and the scientific community to disseminate their ongoing and finalised projects in a concise and informative manner, whether the project has received funding from the European Commission, through one of their current schemes such as with an ERC grant or via Horizon 2020, or has received a grant from one of their National Research Councils or European funding agencies, each project will have the freedom to present their goals, ambitions and up to date research findings to a community that makes a difference to science going forward, from policymakers and public sector to funding agencies and research

councils; Publisher: European Dissemination Media Agency Limited; ISSN 2632-4067; gold publication 2500GBP per 4 pages)

Link: <https://www.europeandissemination.eu/>

- **Projects magazine** (print and digital publication that has established itself at the forefront of European innovation, research and development by disseminating knowledge about the latest research projects, investment and policy to all the major stakeholders involved in driving forward European research and innovation, the magazine is circulated 8 times per year to over 10,000 industry professionals selected for their position, influence and spending power in the development of science and technology across Europe. Projects have a readership of over 40,000 and the magazine has helped over 800 research projects reach a pan-European audience over the past 6 years; Publisher: Insight Publishers, UK)

Link: <https://ipl.eu.com/research-dissemination/projects-magazine/>

TABLE 2 LIST OF PUBLICATIONS PLANNED FOR POWERSKIN+

Publication title	Link	Publication type	DOI	ISSN or eSSN	Authors	Periodical name/ Publisher	Number, Date	Place	Relevant pages	Public & private participation	Peer/ review	Open access, cost of publication	Partner/s	Status
TBC	TBC	Publication in Magazine	TBC	ISSN: 2219-9446 ISBN: 978-92-64-28230-8	TBC	European Energy Innovation (EEI) Magazine, Prologue Media Limited	Autumn 2020	UK	TBC	NO	NO	YES (Gold), cost 1500EUR per page	FENIX	Planned
TBC	TBC	Publication in Journal	TBC	ISSN 2632-4067	TBC	The Project Repository Journal, European Dissemination Media Agency Limited (EDMA)	Spring 2021	UK	TBC	NO	NO	YES (Gold), cost 2500GBP per 4 pages	FENIX	Planned
TBC	TBC	Publication in Magazine	TBC	TBC	TBC	Projects magazine, Insight Publishers	Autumn 2021	UK	TBC	NO	NO	YES (Gold), cost 2000EUR	FENIX	Planned

10. Press releases

POWERSKIN+ project is going to publish at least two press releases per year about the project important milestones and achievements. First press releases – website launch and Kick-off meeting were shared through project partners’ channels, POWERSKIN+ website and social media profiles. A press release introducing the project’s graphical video, leaflet, and project presentation was posted on BuildUp and EUagenda portals.

FIGURE 16: POWERSKIN+ PRESS RELEASES ON EU AGENDA

FIGURE 17: POWERSKIN+ PRESS RELEASES ON BUILDUP

FIGURE 18: POWERSKIN+ PRESS RELEASES ON FENIX WEBSITE

FIGURE 19: POWERSKIN+ PRESS RELEASES ON IPN WEBSITE

11. Events organization

Final public workshop of the project will be organized with the aim to promote the technology generated during the project as well as to connect EU officials, representative cities, industries, identified stakeholders' segments to the project outcomes. A workshop will be organized close to the demo site to show the concrete project outcomes, technology and application in the real environment.

12. Events participation

To spread awareness about the project to the public, and to attract potential customers or investors, the project will be presented and exhibited at various fairs, expos, exhibitions, workshops and seminars.

Those events in focus:

- **BAU fair in Munich** (world's leading building trade fair for materials, system and architecture/250,000 visitors from 45 countries), <https://bau-muenchen.com/en/>
- **BUDMA fair in Poland** (International construction and architecture fair/46,000 professionals from over 40 countries), <https://www.budma.pl/en>
- **IBF in Czech Republic** (International traditional building fair/43,223 visitors from 20 countries),
- **KLIMAHOUSE in Italy** (trade fair and congress for energy efficiency and sustained building/more than 35.000 visitors), <https://www.fierabolzano.it/it/klimahouse-toscana/home>
- **FORPASIV in Czech Republic** (trade fair for low-energy, passive and zero-energy buildings in Czech Republic/more than 25.000 visitors), <https://forpasiv.cz/>
- **ESE EXPO and IRES Conference in Germany** (International Renewable Energy Storage conference and Energy Storage Europe expo), <https://www.esexpo.com/>
- **MADE Expo in Italy** (hardware and software solutions, construction systems, sustainability of solutions for insulating and protecting living areas, air quality and aesthetic quality, 900 exhibitors, 90,000 visitors), <https://www.madeexpo.it/en/>
- **Portugal smart cities summit** (9,300 visitors, 200 exhibitors, 100 speakers), <https://portugalsmartcities.fil.pt/>
- **World Sustainable Energy Days conference in Austria** (around 100,000 visitors), <https://www.wsed.at/en/world-sustainable-energy-days.html>
- **Sustainable Places conference in France** (180 registrants, 15 Clustering Workshops), <https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/>
- **Green week conference in Brussels** (approximately 400 000 visitors every year), <https://www.eugreenweek.eu/en>

12.1 List of dissemination events and activities

POWERSKIN+ partners have identified prospective dissemination events they are going to participate and present POWERSKIN+ project mainly for the upcoming year. At this stage, there are several events that the

project partners already participated in. The list will be updated and extended with new events and activities regularly, at least twice a year. Nonetheless, the recent global situation related to the corona virus strongly affects the events planning.

There are other dissemination and communication activities either performed or planned that can have a significant impact in regard to the widest possible dissemination of Powerskin+ project, e. g. posting on partner's social media profiles, publishing press releases on project partner's websites, presenting the project in other newsletters, showcasing project posters within partner's premises, etc.. Under the current COVID19 crisis, increase the online dissemination and communication activities, such as the ones in social media will be a good mitigation during the rest of the first year of the project to mitigate the lack of events.

Both dissemination events and other dissemination and communication activities are listed in the table below.

TABLE 3 LIST OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION EVENTS AND ACTIVITIES PERFORMED AND PLANNED FOR POWERSKIN+

Type of event	Link	Event/activity title	Objective	Date	Place	Partner contribution	Countries addressed	Target audience and size	Partner	Status
Expo	https://www.techdays.pt/en/techdays http://exameinformativa.sapo.pt/noticias/iniciativas/2019-10-10-Techdays-Ate-sabado-e-possivel-espreitar-o-futuro-em-Aveiro	TECHDAYS	To introduce the project and promote its results.	10th - 12th October 2019	Aveiro, Portugal	Stand (brochures, rollup)	International	Scientific community, industry, +10000 visitors (direct 2000)	IPN	Performed
Press release	https://www.ipn.pt/noticias/noticia/2686?uri=%2F&a=2686	“Kick-off meeting do projeto POWERSKIN+”	To introduce the project and promote its results.	14th October 2019	Internet (IPN website)	Press release posted on partner's website	National (Portuguese language)	IPN customers and partners, general public	IPN	Performed
Roll-up poster exposition	N/A	Sharing project roll-up poster in company premises	To promote project results to IPN's customers and partners	October 2019	Coimbra, Portugal	Sharing project roll-up poster in company premises	National (Portugal)	IPN customers and partners	IPN	Performed
Meeting	N/A	MSc degree class of professor Mizi Fan	Presentation covering an overview of the POWERSKIN+ project for an MSc degree class of Professor Mizi Fan, at the Civil Engineering dept	17th October 2019	London, UK	Project presentation	International	Research community, students, audience 25	BRU	Performed
Leaflet	https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials/leaflets	POWERSKIN+ project leaflet	Promo material design to support project partners during the dissemination events.	1st October 2019	Internet	Design, creation, printing, sharing on the project website, social media	International	General public, industry, research community, at M6 31 downloads from the project website	FENIX	Performed
Roll-up poster	https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials/posters	POWERSKIN+ project roll-up poster	Promo material design to support project partners during the dissemination events.	1st October 2019	Internet	Design, creation, printing, sharing on the project	International	General public, industry, research community, at M6 32	FENIX	Performed

						website, social media		downloads from the project website		
Press release	https://euagenda.eu/publications/powerskin-project-leaflet	Powerskin+ project LEAFLET" is live!	To share short press release about the first POWERSKIN+ promo material through EU Agenda portal.	30th October 2019	Internet	Press release upload on EU Agenda	International	EU Agenda subscribers and visitors, at M6 306 views	FENIX	Performed
Project website	www.powerskinplus.eu	POWERSKIN+ project website	To create a main communication channel for the POWERSKIN+ project.	30th November 2019	Internet	Project website design and creation, maintenance and monthly update	International	General public, industry, research community, at M6 3 344 views	FENIX	Performed
Press release	https://fenixtnt.cz/project/powerskin-	POWERSKIN+ project	Promotion of POWERSKIN+ project through the FENIX website.	November 2019	Internet	Press release posted on partner's website	International	FENIX customers and partners.	FENIX	Performed
Project social media	https://twitter.com/PowerskinPlus https://www.facebook.com/powerskinplus https://www.linkedin.com/company/28835978 https://www.instagram.com/powerskinplus/	POWERSKIN+ social network profiles	To establish a social media campaign for the POWERSKIN+ project.	1st October 2019	Internet	Social networks creation (FB, Twitter, LI, Instagram) and weekly updates	International	General public, industry, research community, at M6 160 followers in total	FENIX	Performed
Conference	https://sites.google.com/fct.unl.pt/facades19/home?authuser=0	FACADES 2019 - South Challenge sand Beyond	The annual European Façade Network Conference (FACADES19) focused on the need to determine possible design options and effective strategies for adapting buildings to climate challenges consequences. The goal was to bring together, a multi-disciplinary group of scientists and facade designers, specialists, consultants,	22nd November 2019	Lisbon, Portugal	Project presentation (IPN disseminated the project on informal contacts, POLITO presented the keynote) Within the presentation of POLITO research activity on	International	Scientists and facade designers, specialists, consultants, manufacturers, builders etc. and young researchers, audience about audience 100	IPN/ POLITO	Performed

			manufacturers, builders etc. and young researchers, from Europe and other parts of the world to present and exchange new ideas and concepts, work in progress, case studies and results relating to building facades.			multifunctional building envelopes				
BuildUp post	https://www.buildup.eu/en/explore/links/powerskin-project-leaflet	POWERSKIN+ project leaflet	Project leaflet promotion through thematic portal.	November 2019	Internet	Press release upload on BuildUp portal	International	BuildUp members (other EU projects, industry, scientific community), at M6 549 views	FENIX	Performed
Press release	https://www.ipn.pt/noticias/noticia/2731?uri=%2Fnoticias	POWERSKIN + launches new website	Promotion of POWERSKIN website through the IPN website.	10th December 2019	Internet (IPN website)	Press release posted on partner's website	International	IPN customers and partners, general public	IPN	Performed
Social media	https://www.facebook.com/institutopedronunes/posts/10156396971622610	POWERSKIN+ launches new website	Promotion of POWERSKIN website through the IPN social network profiles.	December 2019	Internet	Post on Partner's social media	International	PN customers and partners, general public	IPN	Performed
Video	https://www.powerskinplus.eu/videos https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZRKY-My3inc	POWERSKIN+ project graphical video	To create POWERSKIN+ project video as part of the promotion package.	November 2019	Internet	Design, creation, sharing on the project website, social media	International	General public, on YouTube at M6 134 views	FENIX	Performed
Project presentation	https://www.powerskinplus.eu/documents/promo-materials/presentations	POWERSKIN+ project presentation	To create POWERSKIN+ project presentation as part of the promotion package.	November 2019	Internet	Design, creation, sharing on the project website, social media	International	General public, Downloads from project web at M6 58	FENIX	Performed
Conference	https://www.ashrae.org/conferences/conference-resources/past-ashrae-conferences	ASHRAE - 2019 Buildings XIV International Conference	To introduce POWERSKIN+ project (within the presentation of POLITO research activity on multifunctional building envelopes).	December 2019	Clearwater, Florida	Presentation and paper	International	Professionals, Researchers, USA DoE (Dept of Energy) Members, Audience 150	POLITO	Performed

Meeting	https://www.ipn.pt/noticias/noticia/2747?uri=%2Fnoticias%2Fmaisnoticias%3Fnoticia%3Dtrue%26tema%3D11%26page%3D2%26%3D1584025040825	POWERSKIN+ project presentation	Presentation covering an overview of the POWERSKIN+ project. China Academy of Building Research.	December 2019	Beijing, China	Speech, ppt	International	Scientific community, industry, audience 10	IPN	Performed
Meeting	https://www.ipn.pt/noticias/noticia/2747?uri=%2Fnoticias%2Fmaisnoticias%3Fnoticia%3Dtrue%26tema%3D11%26page%3D2%26%3D1584025040825	POWERSKIN+ project presentation	Presentation covering an overview of the POWERSKIN+ project. Fujian Agriculture and Forestry University	January 2020	Fozhou, China	Speech, ppt	International	Scientific community, industry, audience 80	IPN	Performed
Visit	https://www.ipn.pt/noticias/noticia/2747?uri=%2Fnoticias%2Fmaisnoticias%3Fnoticia%3Dtrue%26tema%3D11%26page%3D2%26%3D1584025040825	POWERSKIN+ project presentation	Presentation covering an overview of the POWERSKIN+ project. Supertech – Advanced Material Co.	January 2020	Fujian, China	Presentation	International	Industry	IPN	Performed
Press release	https://euagenda.eu/videos/35951	Powerskin+ project introduction video	To share short press release about the first POWERSKIN+ promo material through EU Agenda portal.	20th of January 2020	Internet	Press release upload on EU Agenda	International	EUAgenda subscribers and followers, KPIs tracked via YouTube	FENIX	Performed
Press release	https://www.buildup.eu/en/explore/links/powerskin-introduction-video	Powerskin+ project introduction video	To share short press release about the first POWERSKIN+ promo material through EU Agenda portal.	20th of January 2020	Internet	Press release upload on BuildUp portal	International	BuildUp subscribers and followers, at M6 173 views	FENIX	Performed
Social media posts	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6588411427441131520 https://www.facebook.com/sauletech/photos/a.424272317934042/942604519434150/?type=1&theater	POWERSKIN+ kick-off meeting	Sharing information about the start of the project	October 11, 2019	Internet	Project promotion on partner's social media channels	International	8 473 followers at M6 in total (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter)	Saule Technologies	Performed

	https://twitter.com/SauleTech/status/1182648624838258692									
Social media posts	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6626047989561470976 https://www.facebook.com/sauletech/posts/1041000716261196?_tn=-R https://twitter.com/SauleTech/status/1220286675173224449	POWERSKIN+ project leaflet	Promoting the project's leaflet	January 23, 2020	Internet	Project promotion on partner's social media channels	International	8 473 followers at M6 in total (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter)	Saule Technologies	Performed
Press release	https://www.uceeb.cz/aktuality/zapojili-j sme-se-do-mezinarodniho-projektu-powerskin	Zapojili jsme se do mezinárodního projektu POWERSKIN+	Promotion of POWERSKIN+ website through the CVUT UCEEB website.	16th January 2020	Internet	Press release posted on partner's website	National (Czech language)	General public	CVUT	Performed
Social media	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cvut-uceeb_zapojili-j sme-se-do-mezin%C3%A1rodn%C3%ADho-projektu-activity-6623481555929055232-LM20	Zapojili jsme se do mezinárodního projektu POWERSKIN+	Promotion of POWERSKIN+ website through the CVUT UCEEB social network.	16th January 2020	Internet	Press release posted on partner's social network	National (Czech language)	General public	CVUT	Performed
Twitter	https://twitter.com/FENIXTNT1/status/1205073946015621120	Brand manual shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN+ Brand manual	12th December 2019	Internet	Twitter FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 195 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed
Twitter	https://twitter.com/FENIXTNT1/status/1186279175189073921	Designed promo materials shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN+ Promo material	21st October 2019	Internet	Twitter FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 195 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed
Twitter	https://twitter.com/FENIXTNT1/status/1180019017223946240	Invitation on KICK OFF meeting shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN+ new project	4th October 2019	Internet	Twitter FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 195 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/posts/2572791946285189?_tn=-R	Brand manual shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN+ Brand manual	12th December 2019	Internet	Facebook FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 81 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/fenixtnt.cz/po	promo shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN+ project promo	21st October 2019	Internet	Facebook FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 81 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed

	sts/2522166518014399?_tn=-R									
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/fenixnt.cz/photos/a.1535664493331278/2506170619613989/?type=3&theater	kick-off meeting shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN kick-off meeting	4th October 2019	Internet	Facebook FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 81 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6610840265328590849	shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN+	12th December 2019	Internet	LinkedIn FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 74 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6592044123719643136	"We are really happy to be a part of the new #H2020" shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN+ leaflet and rollout	21st October 2019	Internet	LinkedIn FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 74 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6585778837781651456	Next week we start the project with a Kick-off meeting shared on Fenix profile	Increase the visibility of POWERSKIN+ kick-off meeting	4th October 2019	Internet	LinkedIn FENIX	International	FENIX followers, 74 followers at M6	FENIX	Performed
Workshop	https://thermoss.eu/workshopbe/	Thermoss project public workshop - Advanced technologies for heating and cooling at building and district level	Introducing POWERSKIN+ via promo material and presentation.	27th of February 2020	Brussels, Belgium	Promo materials and presentation distribution	International	Industry professionals, wide public, other H2020 projects representatives, policymakers, audience 30	FENIX	Performed
Press release	https://www.buildup.eu/en/news/powerskin-project-updated-promo-material	Powerskin+ project: updated promo material	To promote updated promo material on the BuildUp portal.	28th February 2020	Internet	Press release upload on BuildUp Portal	International	BuildUp subscribers and followers, at M6 171 views	Fenix	Performed
Press release	https://euagenda.eu/publications/powerskin-project	POWERSKIN+ Project	To present the project by uploading the .ppt presentation to EU Agenda portal	February 2020	Internet	Press release upload on EU Agenda portal	International	EUAgenda subscribers and followers, at M6 32 views	FENIX	Performed
Press release	https://euagenda.eu/publications/powerskin-project-brochure	POWERSKIN+ Project brochure	To promote updated promo material on the EU Agenda portal.	February 2020	Internet	Press release uploaded on EU Agenda Portal	International	EUAgenda subscribers and followers, at M6 34 views	FENIX	Performed

Visit	https://www.ipn.pt/noticias/noticia/2762?uri=%2Fnoticias%3Ftema%3D11	IPN receives a visit from the Canadian Embassy	The Pedro Nunes Institute was visited by the Commercial Counsellor of the Canadian Embassy, Anne-Marie Parent, and by the Advisor for Foreign Policy and Communication Affairs at the Canadian Embassy, Eurico Mendes Nobre. They were received by the director of the Pedro Nunes Institute, Professor Teresa Mendes. They got to know the Pedro Nunes Institute better and how it works. Potential synergies between the two institutions were identified. They visited three of our laboratories: the Automation and Systems Laboratory (LAS), Informatics and Systems Laboratory (LIS) and the Testing, Wear and Materials Laboratory (LED & MAT) and got to know their main projects.	11th February 2020	Coimbra, Portugal	Project presentation, brochures, rollup	International	Counsellor of the Embassy, Advisor for Foreign Policy and Communication Affairs, IPN representatives, audience 10	IPN	Performed
Visit	https://www.ipn.pt/noticias/noticia/2764?uri=%2Fnoticias%3Ftema%3D11	IPN receives a visit from the British Embassy	British Ambassador Chris Santy visited the Pedro Nunes Institute. He was received by the director of Instituto Pedro Nunes, Professor Teresa Mendes, and by the director of Incubation and Acceleration, Dr. Paulo Santos. The	13th February 2020	Coimbra, Portugal	Project presentation, brochures, rollup	International	British Ambassador, IPN representatives, audience 10	IPN	Performed

			Ambassador got to know the Pedro Nunes Institute better and how it works. Potential synergies between the two institutions were identified. He visited our Testing, Wear and Materials Laboratory (LED & MAT), during which Engineer João Paulo Dias and researcher Jorge Corker made their main projects known.							
Fair and Conference	https://www.eseeexpo.com/	Energy Storage Europe Expo - The leading international fair for energy storage systems	Introducing POWERSKIN + via promo material and presentation	Postponed with no new date due to Corona virus, originally 10-13 March 2020	Düsseldorf, Germany	Promo materials and presentation distribution via booth	International	Industry professionals, wide public, audience TBC	FENIX	Planned
Conference	https://www.sustainableplaces.eu/	Sustainable Places 2020 - Conference on Circular Economy, Digital Twins, BIPV, Local Energy Communities, Sustainable Digital Infrastructure, and as always, all sustainability topics	Introducing POWERSKIN + via promo material and presentation	Postponed due to Corona virus 28-30 October 2019, originally 3-5 June 2020	Aix-Les Bains, France	Promo materials and presentation distribution	International	Industry professionals, wide public, audience TBC	FENIX	Planned
Newsletter	TBC European Enterprise Network newsletter	POWERSKIN+ - Environment and Sustainable Construction (title TBC)	TBC	2021	TBC	TBC	International	TBC	AMS/IPN	Planned
Exhibition	http://www.verde-tec.gr/el/default.asp?sw=1366	"Verde.tec – Environmental technologies 4th	Introducing POWERSKIN + via promo material	29-31 May 2020	Athens, Greece	Promo material in booth	International	Architects, Contractors, Investors in	AMS	Planned

		international exhibition "						RES, agents and dealers from all over Greece and abroad, foreign, Individuals interested in photovoltaic, bio-purification and water quality or energy saving systems on their property.		
Confere nce	www.powerskin.org	PowerSKIN Conference, to be held at the trade fair BAU	The conference aims to discuss the future role of building skin to achieve carbon neutral building stocks.	January 14, 2021	Munich, Germany	Promo materials, project presentation	International	Industry professionals, academia	POLITO /FENIX /IPN	Planned

13. Cluster activities

Project partners will seek collaboration with other H2020 projects that could complement activities and provide synergies enhancing dissemination. By month M6, one cluster partnership has been established with the project “[Switch2Save](#)”. The first planned event together is workshop “Energy Efficient Technologies for Building Envelopes” organized by Switch2Save project on **25th – 27th November 2020** at Fraunhofer FEP, Dresden, Germany.

FIGURE 20: WORKSHOP “ENERGY EFFICIENT TECHNOLOGIES FOR BUILDING ENVELOPES” FLYER

14. Liaison with EU communities

Project partners are going to get in contact with relevant European communities involving potentially interested stakeholders, including the European technology platforms and Public-Private Partnership as ECTP, the E2B initiative, the BuildUP initiative, etc.

FIGURE 21: POWERSKIN+ ON ECTP PORTAL

15. Training activities

Training activities (courses, webinars, guidelines, videos) will be organized to share the generated knowledge to professionals that might be involved in various stages of the production, application or installation of the POWERSKIN+ technology.

16. Proof of events already performed

Project partners are required to provide to dissemination leader (FENIX) proof of dissemination and communication events and activities they already participated (e.g. photos, presentations, videos, website link, press release, etc.). Some of these passed events are presented below.

Table 2b: Proof of events already performed	
Event title	Facades 2019, Lisbon, Portugal, 22 November 2019
Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)	

Table 2b: Proof of events already performed	
Event	TechnDays 2019, Aveiro, Portugal, October 2019
Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)	

Table 2b: Proof of events already performed	
Event title	MSc degree class of professor Mizi Fan, 17th October 2019, Loindon, UK
Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)	

Table 2b: Proof of events already performed	
Event title	China, December 2019/January 2020
Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)	

Table 2b: Proof of events already performed	
Event title Thermoss project Public workshop, 27th of February 2020, Brussels, Belgium Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)	
Table 2b: Proof of events already performed	
Event title IPN receives a visit from the Canadian Embassy, 11th February 2020 Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)	
Table 2b: Proof of events already performed	
Event title IPN receives a visit from the Canadian Embassy, 13th February 2020 Attachments (agenda, photos, pictures, videos, ppt, etc.)	

FIGURE 22: PHOTOS FROM PERFORMED EVENTS

17. Conclusion

This report describes the first release of the Communication and Dissemination Plan and strategy, the definition of the target groups, dissemination channels, partners' roles and responsibilities, and the dissemination and communication actions already identified, performed and planned for the POWERSKIN+ project. Dissemination activities are going to be undertaken at national, international and EU level by all POWERSKIN+ partners from the beginning of the project to its very end. The activities will be tracked and the plan will be updated every year.

